

Managing Board Meeting Agenda & Minutes

Date: Thursday, 6th March 2025
Time: 14:00 - 15:00 CET / 13:00-14:00 GMT
Venue: Virtual

Call-in details:

Meeting ID:
Passcode:

[Agenda/Minutes folder](#)

Attendees	
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Apologies	Rafael Andrade Buono (VIB, BE),
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AGENDA

Action items	1
Priority topics for discussion	1
Project monitoring	4
AoB	4

No.	Item	Type	Presented by
1	Action items		

Who	What	Due	Please Update

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2	<p>Priority topics for discussion</p> <p><i>Please add below urgent/important topics that required discussion</i></p>		
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Priority Topics: (please add topics with a short explanation)

- **Amendments**
 - EC review pending
- **General Assembly Feedback**
 - Ethics/AI advice
- **Cross-WP topic**
 - Policy Brief on Credit and Recognition? (M18)
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- **WP topic deep dive**
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- **Work Package updates**

WP1 - Coordination and support (Mado/Juan)	
Progress & Decisions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● M1.2 ready to submit ● T1.5 GEAM tool survey draft
Plans	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● D1.2 Updated Data Management Plan due in April
Problems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ●
Support required	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ●
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ●

WP2 - Implementation of research software best practices through ELIXIR Communities (Silvio/Fotis/John/Federica)	
Progress & Decisions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● started series of short presentations to highlight ELIXIR Nodes' activities related to software quality ● M2.3 Hackathon with selected communities accepted at AHM: taking place June 5 and June 6 (at CERTH)

